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FIRST RECORD OF *POLYMIXIA NOBILIS* LOWE, 1836 IN BENIN CONTINENTAL SHELF (GULF OF GUINEA)

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Abstract

Two specimens of the fish species stout beardfish (*Polymixia nobilis*) were collected from the fishermen catch at Cotonou Port in Benin. The current report represents the first record of *Polymixia nobilis* in Benin continental shelf. Nethertheless they found it in Sierra Leone. FAO not yet mentioned in Gulf Of Guinea biodiversity till to now. From this time to now no more specimen was collected.

Keywords: New record, Benin, Continental shelf, *Polymixia nobilis*

Introduction

The stout beardfish is a deep water fish of the Eastern and Western Atlantic ocean, with a geographical range that extends from West Indies, Saba Bank, Leeward Islands, off northern coast of Cuba and west of the Bahamas; reported to occur in the northern coast of South America, as far north as 43.67°N (WoRMS taxon detail). The specie was not documented in all countries in Gulf Of Guinea by FAO (Schneider 1990) and particularly during the survey in FAO zone 34.

The capture of a specimen of *Polymixia nobilis*, a rare species in the eastern Atlantic waters north of the Canary and Madeira Islands, is reported as the first record in the vicinity of the Strait of Gibraltar (Farias & al. 2007).

To date, stout beardfish has been confirmed to occur in many countries. It's distributed across the Atlantic Ocean. In the eastern central Atlantic (ECA) it is known from the Corner Rise seamount, the Azores, Madeira, Greater Meteor seamount, Seine and Sedlo seamount, the Canary Islands, Cape Verde and St. Helena Islands. It has a disjunct distribution in the ECA and is found around oceanic islands. In the western Atlantic it is known from Florida, Bermuda, the Bahamas,

Cuba and the eastern and northern Gulf of Mexico, Lesser Antilles and from Panama to the French Guiana. It is found from 70-800 m depth, but more commonly between 360-540 m (Moore 2002).

According to red list, Native countries are: Anguilla; Antigua and Barbuda; Aruba; Bahamas; Barbados; Bermuda; Bonaire, Sint Eustatius and Saba; Brazil; Cape Verde; Colombia; Cuba; Curaçao; Dominica; Dominican Republic; Grenada; Guadeloupe; Guyana; Haiti; Martinique; Mexico; Montserrat; Morocco; Panama; Portugal (Azores, Madeira, Selvagens); Puerto Rico; Saint Barthélemy; Saint Helena, Ascension and Tristan da Cunha (Saint Helena (main island)); Saint Kitts and Nevis; Saint Lucia; Saint Martin (French part); Saint Vincent and the Grenadines; Sierra Leone; Sint Maarten (Dutch part); Spain (Canary Is.); Suriname; Trinidad and Tobago; Turks and Caicos Islands; United States; Venezuela, Bolivarian Republic of; Virgin Islands, British; Virgin Islands, U.S.; Western Sahara.

FAO Native region are: Atlantic – western central; Atlantic – southeast; Atlantic – eastern central; Atlantic – northeast; Atlantic – northwest (map N°1).

Note: Distribution range colors indicate degree of suitability of habitat which can be interpreted as probabilities of occurrence.

Legend

<p>Relative probabilities of occurrence</p>	<p>Explore native range map</p> <p>Explore suitable habitat map</p> <p>Explore point map</p> <p>Show mapping parameters</p> <p>Create your own map</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">More species data:</p> <p>List of countries</p> <p>List of FAO areas</p> <p>List of ecosystems</p>
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Distribution maps for *Polymixia nobilis* (Stout beardfish), with modelled year 2100 native range map based on IPCC A2 emissions scenario.

Source: www.aquamaps.org, version of Aug. 2013. Web.

Description

The bathydemersal species is usually found on semi-hard and soft bottoms on the continental shelves and slopes (Fock and *al.* 2002). It is found from 70-800 m depth (Moore 2002), but more commonly from 360-540 m. It is associated with a variety of deep-water structures, such as seamounts in the Azores (Pakhorukov 2008), and flat hard-bottom habitat off the coast of the eastern USA characterized by carbonate bedrock with little to no vertical relief, and patchy cover of small scleractinian and stylasterid corals (Wieber 2008) though it is not a dominant component of the species assemblage in terms of numbers or biomass in these habitats.

Diagnosis: body deep and compressed, deepest at level of dorsal fin origin (depth nearly one-third of total length). Eye large; snout short and rounded; dorsal profile of head rounded; snout projecting beyond lower jaw; maxilla very broad posteriorly and extending backward beyond eye; mouth large, horizontal; small teeth in villiform bands in both jaws, teeth also present on vomer and palatines; margin of preopercle weakly serrated; a pair of long chin barbels inserted well behind symphysis of lower jaw. Gillrakers 3 on upper, and 8 on lower branch of first gill arch. Dorsal fin with 4-6 spines graduated in size and 30-38 soft rays, the anterior ones very long, forming an elevated lobe; anal fin with 3 or 4 short spines and 16-18 soft rays, beginning below the posterior portion of dorsal fin; pectoral fins with 1 spine and 6 soft rays; caudal fin forked. Body covered with large, ctenoid scales; head scaled, except on the preopercle; scales on top of head extending forward almost to nostrils; lateral line scales 45-54. Colour: greyish to greenish, the head darker; lobes of dorsal, anal and caudal fins marginate with black. Size: to 35 cm SL, usually 20-25 cm.

Relevant biological parameters (reproduction, growth and feeding habits) were recently collected for this species with the expressed aim of allowing the future implementation of regulatory measures for the sustainability of the fisheries and conservation of this species in the Canary Islands (García-Mederos *et al.* 2010).

In European waters *Polymixia nobilis* occurs frequently in the Canary Islands (Franquet and Brito 1995, Brito *et al.* 2002, García-Mederos *et al.* 2010). Delgado (2007) indicates the species to occur frequently off Madeira, Porto Santo and the Desertas islands. In survey cruises off the Azores, Menezes (2003) found the species to be rare.

Elsewhere in the Macaronesian area, the species is also common in seamounts, islets and islands off the Cape Verde archipelago (Menezes *et al.* 2004). The populations of *P. nobilis* in the area are subject to small scale exploitation, in a context of multispecies fisheries using hook-and-line and bottom longlines.

Material and Methods

Polymixia nobilis were with the fishmonger in fishing harbor during the follow up of biodiversity. According to them, the species were caught with a net. After observation, individuals are weighed and measured.

During inventory at the landing area with the fishmonger 21 November 2016 we find two specimen of stout beardfish. These specimen was preserved in 70% of alcohol (fig.2) at the Applied Ecological Laboratory of Abomey-Calavi University.

Results and Discussion

Systematics of the species

Animalia (Kingdom), Chordata (Phylum), Vertebrata (Subphylum), Gnathostomata (Infraphylum), Osteichthyes (Parvphylum), Actinopterygii (Gigaclass), Actinopteri (Class), Teleostei (Subclass), Polymixiiformes (Order), Polymixiidae (Family), *Polymixia* (Genus), *Polymixia nobilis* (Species)

The capture of a specimen of *Polymixia nobilis*, a rare species in the eastern Atlantic waters central, is reported as the first record in Benin continental shelf. The specimens was caught by gill nets named "Tohounga" in local language. This engine usually caught a lot of diversity of fish.

The genus *Polymixia* (Lowe 1838) currently comprises ten marine species. Only two of them are present in the Atlantic Ocean, *Polymixia nobilis* (Lowe 1838) and *Polymixia lowei* (Günther 1859). The Atlantic beardfish (*P. nobilis*) is a bathydemersal marine fish occurring in tropical and subtropical waters over the outer continental shelf and slope, around islands and on seamounts at depths ranging from 100 to 770 m (Hureau 1984). It is usually found on soft and semi-hard bottoms. Two specimens of *P. nobilis* was identified at the Port jetty with artisanal fishermen.

Even in Fishbase a few information on the species available like missing range of Maturity size ; Maturity length $L_m = 26.0$, range 20 - ? cm Max length : 48.0 cm.

Estimate weight for given length = 13 cm correspond to 28.19 g ; The length to weight ratio is 0.42 at fishbase and in our case it is 0.45; these two values show that the growth is then linked to the environmental conditions.

Photo1: Two specimens collected in 2016

Photo 2: One specimen

Table 2

Meristic data of the specimens

Charcteritics	1	2
Lt	36	36
Lf	31	31
Ls	29	29
Eyes diameter	31	31
Barbel length	06	06
Eyes to Head length	11	11
Mouth to Eyes length	2.1	2.1
Weight	700g	695g
Body round	25cm	25cm

Morphometric characteristic

Dorsal spines (total): 5; Dorsal soft rays (total): 35; Anal spines: 4; Anal soft rays: 15; Vertebrae: 29. Dark brownish grey in color, silvery below; black blotch on distal part of anterior dorsal rays. Snout blunt, rounded, adipose. Hyoid barbels present.

Polymixia nobilis is found around oceanic islands and seamounts. It is targeted in some small-scale fisheries, but is mostly taken as incidental bycatch, particularly in seamount fisheries targeting *Beryx* spp. However, this is not a major threat. Therefore, it is listed as Least Concern

A single sighting is insufficient to indicate that a viable population of Atlantic humpback dolphins is present in Benin or the northern Gulf of Guinea. Indeed, the conservation status of the species remains very unclear throughout its range and previous concerns regarding low population sizes, high exposure to potential anthropogenic impacts and a limited near-shore distribution continue to be highly relevant.

Nevertheless, the Benin sighting provides continued optimism for locating extant populations of the stout beardfish in other potential range states including Guinea, Liberia, Côte d'Ivoire, Ghana, Togo, Nigeria, Equatorial Guinea and the Democratic Republic of the Congo. As previously highlighted determining the status of this species should be a conservation priority and urgently requires systematic and focused research effort throughout its geographical range (both confirmed and potential range states).

Polymixia nobilis occurs frequently in the Canary Islands (Garcia-Mederos et al. 2010). Experimental fishing surveys carried out on the Sierra Leone Rise by

Spanish commercial vessels captured this species in the vicinity of seamounts. *Polymixia nobilis*, which was captured at depths ranging from 707-1,174 m, was considered a discard species, not of interest to large commercial fleets. It was present in low numbers at all sampled seamounts (Ramos et al. 2001).

Polymixia nobilis is abundant in museum collections (56 lots), and lots typically contain one to two individuals, although several lots contain >4 individuals (Fishnet2 2013).

The species is subject to small-scale exploitation in a context of multi-species fisheries, but there are no other specific threats to *P. nobilis*. In the Canary Islands, catches are relatively important within the local small-scale fisheries. The species is fished year round with line-and-hook (mainly off El Hierro Island) and trammel nets (mainly in the eastern sector of Tenerife Island).

In European waters, *Polymixia nobilis* is taken in a small-scale demersal fishery off the islands of Gran Canaria and El Hierro (Canary Islands) by handline and bottom drop line which primarily target *Beryx splendens*. Separate statistics are not reported, however catches are aggregated with targeted *Beryx* spp. and range from 2.5 tonnes in 1991 to 17.5 tonnes in 1995 (Rico et al. 2001, Durr and Gonzalez 2002). This is a relatively important local, small-scale fishery, in the Canaries (Garcia-Mederos et al. 2010).

The fish specimen is kept in the laboratory museum in 70 ° alcohol in the bottle. We trained student on the species (Photo 3).

Photo 3: Two specimens in alcohol in the museum

Conclusion

This species is identified once in Benin continental shelf. Since the first record, there was no more observation. Monitoring of marine species continue with fishermen along the beach and onboard the trawler; so we hope that we could find other specimen in the future. The fishermen don't know this species name in vernacular language; thus we can confirm that they never meet the species during their activities. Till to now, we didn't observe another specimen. We follow to now exactly why the species appear in Benin catch.

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